

**OPTIMIZATION OF FLEXIBLE STRUCTURE
MADE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
FOR HIGH SPEED ROBOTS**

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ABSTRACT

The operating speed and endpoint positional accuracy of existing industrial manipulators are limited by the inertial and stiffness characteristics of the articulating members of the robot's mechanical linkage. This limitation may be overcome by developing members having high structural stiffness and strength with low mass. These characteristics can be obtained by fabricating the arms of the manipulator in CFRP (carbon fibre reinforced plastic) composite materials. Moreover, organic matrix composite materials exhibit a structural damping capacity from 10 to 100 times that of usual materials. For symmetric multilayers composite materials, this structural damping may be controlled by the choice of an optimal orientation of the fibres and usefully exploited in robot design to dissipate transient vibrations at the termination of endpoint maneuvers, thereby reducing the settling time.

Keywords : - Flexible Robotic Arm - Composite Materials -

1. INTRODUCTION

For most robots used at present, arm rigidity is calculated so that their static and dynamic deflections are in accordance with the precision required for positioning of the object to be manipulated. Where weight and size constraints are important, a solution is to concede a certain flexibility of the arms and to take this into account in the design of the control law. Here, transfers no longer only concern inertia, but also more complex transfers, where such parameters appear as the flexural rigidity and the damping capacity of the material used. The

control-structure interdependence [1], [2], [3] shows that it is desirable to achieve a mechanical structure with as much structural damping as possible. Achieving high dynamics implies lightweight structures, thus pointing to the use of composite materials. Some organic matrix composites have a structural damping capacity from 10 to 100 times that of usual materials such as light alloys. However, optimization is faced with the rigidity-damping dilemma. In fact, for symmetric multilayers composite materials, maximum mechanical resistance is obtained for fibre orientations of 0° from the solicitation axis, whereas maximum damping is achieved at 45° where shearing is maximal. Optimization, then consists in determining a structure, given fixed dynamics for control, with sufficient rigidity, and optimal damping, to reduce rapidly the superfluous oscillations due to flexibility. These oscillations reduce the admissible stress defined by the optimization of the open-loop's and then reduce the rapidity of the closed loop.

2. TRANSFERS OBTAINED FROM MODELLING OF A FLEXIBLE STRUCTURE

Figure (1) gives an outline of the mechanical model of robot movements with a flexible segment in plane motion.

Figure 1 - Plane motion of a flexible segment.

The position of a point P on the arm is defined by :

$$\begin{aligned} X_p(x) &= x \cos(q_1) - w(x, t) \sin(q_1) \\ Y_p(x) &= x \sin(q_1) + w(x, t) \cos(q_1) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The flexible segment can be modelled by a Bernoulli-Euler beam where the local equation for small movements is :

$$EI w_{,xxxx}(x, t) + \mu w_{,tt}(x, t) = 0, \tag{2}_b$$

oundary conditions being :

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0 \quad & w(x, t) = 0 \\ & EI w_{,xx}(x, t) = J_r w_{,xtt}(x, t) \\ x = L \quad & EI w_{,xx}(x, t) = -J_s w_{,xtt}(x, t) \\ & EI w_{,xxx}(x, t) = M_s w_{,tt}(x, t) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where L is beam length, E the Young's modulus of the material, I the quadratic momentum of the beam, μ the uniform density of the beam, J_r the inertia of the rotor motor, M_s the mass of

the end load, J_s the inertia of the end load and using the classical notation :
 $w_{,x}(x,t) = \partial w(x,t)/\partial x$.

The assumed modes technique permits developing $w(x,t)$ on the basis of the assumed modes shapes of the free oscillation problem, that is, by choosing to take only two modes into account :

$$w(x,t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 f_i(x) g_i(t) , \quad (4)$$

with :

$$f_i(x) = \frac{J_r k_i^3}{2\mu} \{ [\cos(k_i x) - \text{ch}(k_i x) + \sin(k_i x)] + a [\cos(k_i x) - \text{ch}(k_i x) + \text{sh}(k_i x)] \} , \quad (5)$$

k_i being solution of the frequency equation :

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{(J_r + J_s) M_s k^4}{\mu^2} - 1 \right] [\text{ch}(kL) \sin(kL) - \cos(kL) \text{sh}(kL)] + \frac{J_r J_s k^6}{\mu^2} [\text{ch}(kL) \sin(kL) + \cos(kL) \text{sh}(kL)] \\ & - \frac{J_r J_s M_s k^7}{\mu^3} [1 + \cos(kL) \text{ch}(kL)] - \frac{J_r k^3}{\mu} [1 + \cos(kL) \text{ch}(kL)] \\ & - \frac{2 J_s k^3}{\mu} \cos(kL) \text{ch}(kL) - \frac{2 M_s k}{\mu} \sin(kL) \text{sh}(kL) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and parameter a given by :

$$a = \frac{\frac{J_r k_i^3}{2\mu} [\sin(k_i L) - \text{sh}(k_i L) + \frac{M_s k_i}{\mu} (\cos(k_i L) - \text{ch}(k_i L))] + \frac{M_s k_i}{\mu} \sin(k_i L) - \text{ch}(k_i L)}{-\frac{J_r k_i^3}{2\mu} [\sin(k_i L) - \text{sh}(k_i L) + \frac{M_s k_i}{\mu} (\cos(k_i L) - \text{ch}(k_i L))] - \frac{M_s k_i}{\mu} \text{sh}(k_i L) - \text{ch}(k_i L)} \quad (7)$$

Let q being the vector of the generalized coordinates :

$$q = [q_1, g_1, g_2]^t , \quad (8)$$

the speed and rate of rotation of an element of the beam at point p can be expressed as :

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X}_p(x) &= v_x(x) \cdot \dot{q} \\ \dot{Y}_p(x) &= v_y(x) \cdot \dot{q} , \\ \dot{\Omega}_p(x) &= v_\Omega(x) \cdot \dot{q} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with in this case ($n=2$) :

$$\begin{aligned} v_x(x) &= [-x \sin(q_1) - f_1 g_1 \cos(q_1) - f_2 g_2 \cos(q_1) ; -f_1 \sin(q_1) ; -f_2 \sin(q_1)] \\ v_y(x) &= [x \cos(q_1) - f_1 g_1 \sin(q_1) - f_2 g_2 \sin(q_1) ; f_1 \cos(q_1) ; f_2 \cos(q_2)] \\ v_\Omega(x) &= [1 ; f_{1,x} ; f_{2,x}] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The inertia matrix $A(q)$ is computed as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} A(q) &= J_1 (v_\Omega(0) \otimes v_\Omega(0)) + J_s (v_\Omega(L) \otimes v_\Omega(L)) + M_s (v_x(L) \otimes v_x(L) + v_y(L) \otimes v_y(L)) \\ &+ \mu \int_0^L [v_x(x) \otimes v_x(x) + v_y(x) \otimes v_y(x)] dx \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

\otimes being the external product of vectors.

The vector of the non-linear terms $B(q,q)$ is given by :

$$b_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(\frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial q_k} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial A_{jk}}{\partial q_i} \right) \dot{q}_j \dot{q}_k \quad i = 1,2,3 . \quad (12)$$

Given the orthogonality relations between the elastic modes shapes on the one hand, and between the elastic and rigid modes shapes on the other, the inertia matrix $A(q)$ is diagonal as is the stiffness matrix K .

This latter is expressed as :

$$K = \text{diag} (k_i) ; k_1 = 0 ; k_i = EI \int_0^l f_{i,xx}(x)^2 dx \quad i = 2,3. \quad (13)$$

Measurements made on symmetric multilayer composite materials for various orientations of the fibres in relation to the sollicitation axis showed that the structural damping capacity ψ was practically constant over a sollicitation frequency range from 10^{-1} et 10^3 Hz. Also, by using the elasticity-viscoelasticity equivalence, it is possible to determine an equivalent viscous damping for each of the structure's modes. The damping matrix thus admits the expression :

$$D = \text{diag} (d_i) ; d_1 = 0 ; d_i = \frac{\psi}{2\pi} a_i \sqrt{\frac{EI k_i^4}{\mu}} \quad i = 2,3. \quad (14)$$

The dynamic model of the robot can be written in the familiar closed form :

$$A(q) \ddot{q} + B(q, \dot{q}) + D \dot{q} + K q = Q \Gamma \quad (15)$$

with $Q = [1, f_{1,x}(0), f_{2,x}(0)]^t$ the input weighting vector and Γ being the joint actuator torque.

By tangent linearisation near the functioning point ($q_0 = 0 ; \dot{q}_0 = 0$) and with the new variables $q = q - q_0 ; \dot{q} = \dot{q} - \dot{q}_0$, we obtain :

$$A(q_0) \ddot{q} + D \dot{q} + K q = Q \Gamma . \quad (16)$$

The angular position of the hub being:

$$\theta = q_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 f_{i,x}(0) g_i , \quad (17)$$

The transition to the operational field permits the description of the transfer function of the robot :

$$G_1(p) = \frac{\theta(p)}{\Gamma(p)} = \frac{1}{a_1 p^2} + \sum_{i=2}^3 \frac{f_{i-1,x}(\theta)^2}{a_i p^2 + d_i p + k_i} , \quad (19)$$

3. CONTROL-STRUCTURE INTERDEPENDANCE

It can be noted that the structural damping of the material comes into play in the computing of critical damping coefficients of each of the second orders of the transfer function $G_1(p)$. The pulsations w_i are a function of the Young's modulus E , of the quadratic momentum I and of the uniform density μ , considering J_r , J_s , and M_s as fixed. Let us make a comparative study of the frequency behavior of the arm for various materials, and, in order to demonstrate the relevance of composite materials, we shall also consider aluminium. Table 1 gives the characteristics of the various materials considered.

The Black loci of transmittance $G_1(j\omega)$ (figure 2) clearly show the diminution of relative amplitudes of the resonance-antiresonance loops as a function of the damping qualities of the material. It can be seen that composite materials provide significantly greater damping factors without exhibiting too low resonance and antiresonance frequencies.

Material	Fibers orientation $\pm \theta$ ($^\circ$)	Young's modulus E (GPa)	Damping capacity Ψ (%)	Volumic mass ρ (kg/m^3)
a) Aluminium		70	0.1	2700
b) Glass-epoxy	50	14.5	18	1700
c) Carbon-epoxy	25	70	8	1700
d) Experimental arm	45	100	2	1700

Table 1 - Features of materials considered

The comparison of these values for the three composite materials clearly illustrates the rigidity-damping dilemma. The more rigid the material chosen (high Young's modulus), the weaker the damping. This is conveyed by the resonance-antiresonance frequency values and the low damping factors.

Figure 2 - Black loci of $G_1(j\omega)$ transmittances

Figure 3 - *Input of the plant corresponding to the closed loop step responses with PD regulator for the materials considered*

The choice of orientation for the experimental arm enables higher frequencies of ω_i and ω_j but at the cost of weaker damping coefficients.

When the dynamics imposed on the control are sufficiently rapid to excite the flexible modes, these latter have a strongly destabilising effect as around their resonance frequency, each one brings about a phase rotation of -180° for a 3 % relative variation of frequency (in the case of composites).

A control strategy aiming to ensure acceptable resonance factors would therefore consist of shifting the $G_1(j\omega)$ Black loci to the right. This can be achieved by a phase advance. This control strategy is based on a PD regulator which provide a phase advance of 50° at the open loop unit gain frequency ω_u fixed at 2 rd/s.

Figure 3 gives the step responses of the control at a step amplitude of 0.05 rd which ensures a 10.5 cm tangential displacement of the arm end.

For materials (b) and (c) displaying the greatest damping, the settle time of the low frequency transitory response is almost equal to the decrease time of the superfluous oscillations, whereas for aluminium (a) these latter continue.

3. RIGIDITY - DAMPING DILEMMA

For a given rigidity, the oscillation amplitude at resonance is inversely proportional to Ψ_0 , so, the better material being that with the highest damping capacity. Of the materials

considered, the better is a $\pm 50^\circ$ carbon-epoxy. However, the comparison of the characteristics of glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy (figure 4) illustrates that carbon fibres are preferable to glass fibres only for fibre orientations under 45° . Glass fibres have higher transversal E_{Tf} and longitudinal shearing G_{LTf} moduli than carbon fibres. Therefore, at a given rigidity, the optimal material is a $\pm 50^\circ$ glass-epoxy (at present a third the cost of carbon).

Figure 4 - Damping capacity and dynamic modulus as a function of the fibres orientation : (---) glass-epoxy ; (—) carbon-epoxy ; (...) plastified carbon-epoxy

The criterium of maximum damping at a given rigidity does not take weight and size into consideration and leads to this paradox of the best "composite" being pure resin.

At a given geometry, with an orientation angle of $\pm 50^\circ$, the optimum laminate glass-epoxy (or the $\pm 50^\circ$ carbon-epoxy where the modulus is more or less the same) must have a moment of inertia 13 times that of a $\pm 15^\circ$ carbon-epoxy to achieve a sixfold damping gain. So if one compares $\pm \theta^\circ$ laminates at a given geometry, the criterium to optimize is no longer the damping Ψ_θ but the product of Ψ_θ and E'_θ . The comparative value of the various laminates (figure 5) is no longer the same as figure 4.

At a given geometry, glass fibres are no longer competitive. The influence of the fibre density is the inverse of that observed at a given rigidity, and the optimum fibre orientation is around 25° . Using the given geometry criterium, the best material is the $\pm 25^\circ$ carbon-epoxy.

Figure 5 - Loss modulus as a function of the fibres orientation :
 (- - -) glass-epoxy ; (—) carbon-epoxy ; (....) plastified carbon-epoxy

4 - CONCLUSION

From the model of a flexible segment, the contributing parameters in the robot transfer expressions have been determined. We have demonstrated that the resonance frequencies and modal damping depend on the mechanical properties of the arm materials.

This approach demonstrates that final performance depends on the consideration of all the elements of the transfer, and on the control-structure interdependence.

From the properties of the materials used, the orientation of fibres permits the optimization of the mechanical characteristics of the structure and indirectly that of frequential performance. This parameter highlights the rigidity-damping dilemma and shows that further criteria must be taken into consideration : given geometry, given rigidity, for a complete specification of the control and of the structure.

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